

THE IMPORTANCE OF VACCINATION IN PREVENTING CORONAVIRUS INFECTION

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The longevity of human life is directly influenced by factors such as environment, climate, heredity, lifestyle, and various diseases.

The average age of people living in the world was 35 years old at the beginning of the last century, but thanks to the help of modern medicine and new technologies, today this indicator is 72 years old.

Humanity has suffered from infectious diseases such as plague, cholera, smallpox, and poliomyelitis since ancient times and suffered great losses. By the time humanity has entered the new millennium, the above-mentioned extremely dangerous infectious diseases have completely disappeared, and in their place, new, highly lethal, extremely dangerous viral diseases, which people have not seen or known before, are emerging.

Changes in the environment, climate, and lifestyle of the population, population density, and the activation of migration processes are causing the widespread spread of some viral infectious diseases worldwide in the form of epidemics and pandemics.

According to the prediction of the United Nations, by 2050, the number of the world's population will reach 10 billion, which in turn will accelerate the processes of migration and urbanization among the population.

The pandemic of Covid-19 infection, which has been ongoing since 2019, has been recognized as an extremely dangerous emergency of international importance in human history.

The Covid-19 pandemic has posed extremely important and serious challenges to the global health care system. The Covid-19 pandemic did not bypass Uzbekistan, this infection spread widely in our country as well. Despite the fact that the epidemiological situation in our republic is relatively stable, the dangerous situation in the world, the emergence of new strains of viruses, demanded immediate prevention of this disease.

The most effective way to fight and prevent the infection of COVID-19 is mass vaccination of the population against this disease.

Measures to vaccinate the population against the coronavirus infection in Uzbekistan began on April 1, 2021 and are now continuing in an organized manner. In Uzbekistan, mass vaccination is carried out with three types of

vaccines: ZF-UZ-VAC 2001, SPUTNIK V, AstraZeneca. All three vaccines have undergone clinical trials.

In order to increase the immunity against coronavirus infection among the population of our country, starting from November 17, 2021, citizens who have received a full vaccine course (those who have been vaccinated 2 or 3 times) are being vaccinated with a booster dose.

Almost all of us know that the infection of Covid-19 is severe, many deaths occur, and it leaves serious complications. Treatment of this disease with the help of drugs is not very effective, therefore, the only way to prevent this disease is vaccination.

Preventive vaccination against many infectious diseases is an effective measure that has been used in the population for many years. Thanks to vaccination, infectious diseases such as smallpox, poliomyelitis, diphtheria have been completely eradicated among mankind, and diseases such as whooping cough, measles, tetanus, and epidemic parotitis have been drastically reduced.

Immunoprophylaxis is one of the most effective measures in the fight against infectious diseases. Advances in the fight against infectious diseases have been linked to vaccination. Some infectious diseases among people (smallpox, poliomyelitis, etc.) were completely eradicated due to mass vaccination of the population.

The program of the World Health Organization to fight against infectious diseases, to completely eliminate some infectious diseases among people, and to drastically reduce some of them, is also based on immunoprophylaxis.

Some progress has been made in the implementation of the vaccination program in Uzbekistan. Vaccination of the population against infectious diseases - the strategy of immunoprophylaxis, raised to the level of state policy, is based on the laws in force in our country, recommendations of the WHO, and this process is convenient, free and aimed at covering wide sections of the population. The new Covid-19 has presented the Ministry of Health, sanitary epidemiology service, all categories of doctors, nurses with the problem of solving important tasks related to the diagnosis, treatment and prevention of this disease.

To ensure the execution of the tasks specified in the order of the Ministry of Health No. 31 of February 15, 2021 "On the preparation and conduct of mass vaccination against the coronavirus infection", to carry out daily monitoring of the ongoing vaccination work, to organize the immunoprophylaxis of the coronavirus infection, according to the age of the population over 18 years old

Lists were drawn up, the population over 65 years of age, medical workers, teachers, employees of pre-school education institutions, armed forces personnel, who should be vaccinated first, were vaccinated next time.

No serious complications or deaths were observed among the vaccinated among our population after vaccination. The concept that the disease is not completely contagious when vaccinated is embedded in the minds of many people. In fact, prophylactic vaccination does not eliminate 100% of disease transmission, viruses can also be transmitted to vaccinated people, but the disease is mild in them, without complications.

According to the latest data from the World Health Organization, more than 200 vaccines against Covid-19 have been developed in most scientific research institutions, many of them have also undergone clinical trials, of which 15 vaccines are recommended for practice. Many citizens are interested in 2-3 vaccinations and ask why such vaccination is needed.

Vaccines are usually administered to the target organism in parts (2-3 times), with certain intervals. This type of vaccination has been used in medicine for a long time, re-introduction of the vaccine into the body of the vaccinated increases the effectiveness of the vaccination, the formation of antibodies increases, antibodies are stored for a long time, which in turn strengthens the ability of the vaccinated person to fight against infection.

Almost all Covid-19 vaccines are given in two or three doses, which in turn increases the protective power of the vaccine.

According to the results of scientific research conducted in many medical institutions of the world, the second re-introduction of the vaccine against Covid-19 into the vaccinated organism increases the protective power of the vaccine several times. Two weeks after the first vaccination, protection against the disease was observed in 52 percent. According to the research results of Israeli scientists, it was found that the titer of antibodies is 6-12 times higher in those who have been vaccinated against Covid-19 than those who have been vaccinated once.

According to experts, it is necessary to take into account the benefits and harms of vaccination against any disease. Today there are contraindications to vaccination against Covid-19 infection: people under 18 years old, pregnant women, nursing mothers, patients during an acute illness and people with hypersensitivity to vaccine proteins are not vaccinated.

The covid-19 pandemic requires the cooperation of all the countries of the world, experts there, to put the results of scientific research into practice, to

develop methods of prevention, diagnosis and treatment of the disease, as well as to develop effective vaccines against this disease. requires.

We recommend that all medical workers, citizens, representatives of the general public follow the opinions and scientifically based recommendations of scientists and leading specialists in the field of early diagnosis, treatment and prevention of the disease and vaccination against it.

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